

Fresh (fragrant) flowers (150 g) of *R. nasuta* collected from our campus during March were extracted with hot 80% ethanol under reflux and the combined extract concentrated *in vacuo*. The aqueous concentrate was fractionated successively with petrol (60-80°); peroxide-free ether and ethylacetate (EtOAc). The petrol and ether fractions on concentration did not yield any crystalline solid. The residue (0.1 g) from the EtOAc fraction was taken up in minimum of Me₂CO and left in an ice-chest for a few days. The dull yellow solid that separated on recrystallisation (twice) from aq. MeOH gave pale yellow needles, m.p. 186-88° (yield 0.04%), λ_{max} (MeOH) 256, 272, 360 nm, which exhibited bathochromic shifts expected of quercetin-3-O-glycoside with various shift reagents⁴ and appeared deep purple under uv turning yellow with NH₃.

To a solution of the glycoside (0.05 g) in hot aq. MeOH (5 ml, 50%), an equal volume of H₂SO₄ (14%) was added and the mixture refluxed at 100° for 2 hrs. The yellow solid that separated from the aqueous hydrolysate was filtered off. It was recrystallised from Me₂CO, m.p. 313-15° (decomp), pentaacetate, m.p. 193-95° and pentamethylether, m.p. 151-53° and was identified as quercetin on the basis of colour reactions, uv data, R_f and the identity confirmed by co- and mixed m.p. with authentic sample as well as its derivatives. The aqueous filtrate after removal of the above aglycone revealed the presence of glucose and rhamnose on PC. The R_f of the glycoside was also indicative of the presence of two sugar moieties. The glycoside was thus characterised as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoglucoside (rutin) and the identity confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample of rutin from *Cleome chelidonii*⁵.

It has been mentioned in the literature that luteolin is a characteristic flavone of the Acanthaceae⁶. The occurrence of chrysoeriol (4'-methoxy-luteolin) and uronides of luteolin and apigenin in this family has also come to light⁷⁻¹⁰. Acanthaceae is well known for unusual flavones¹¹ too. However, there are a few instances of the occurrence of flavonols and their 3-glycosides in this family like kaempferol-3-glucoside and kaempferol-3-sophoroside from *Adhatoda vasica*¹² and kaempferol-3-rungioside from *Rungia repens*¹³. The present report of the isolation of rutin from a plant belonging to the Acanthaceae provides yet another example of the occurrence of a flavonol-3-glycoside in this family which may have biochemical significance.

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Chemical Investigation of *Beaumontia grandiflora* Wall

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BEAUMONTIA grandiflora Wall (Family-Apocynaceae), a woody climber, is sometimes grown in Indian gardens for its showy white flowers. The seeds have been examined for a number of cardenolides²⁻⁴. Literature survey revealed that no work has been done on its leaves and stem. Therefore, the leaves were taken for the present chemical investigation. In all, seven compounds were isolated as reported in Table 1. Two of these were characterised as normal paraffins, two as aliphatic acids, two as triterpenoid compounds, and one as sterol glucoside. It may be mentioned that all these compounds are being reported for the first time in this plant.

Experimental

The powdered plant material was extracted with ethanol and total extractives successively macerated with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and ethylacetate. The chromatographic separation of pet. ether soluble fraction over deactivated alumina (with 1% aqueous acetic acid) led to the isolation of substances A, B, C, D and F while the ethylacetate soluble fraction led to the isolation of substances E and

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